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PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

VOLUME 1

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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“SILENT CHAINS: THE UNSEEN STRUGGLE”

In your purple cave where the silence grieves,
A story is told, a secret is kept.

Where dreams should soar and reach the stars,
Motivation doors left open are locked by chains of despair.

And they seduce the gentle hearted with soft-spoken lies,
Sweet promise, dark futures.

Where selling hope in the streets is a crowded business,
A heart that was once bright is now ensnared and frozen.

Behind the door, the screams echo,
In secret places where souls can be found.

The secret world, that creepy plight,
The lost dreams slipping out of view.

But in the night a fire is started,
A voice that rises, a call to arms.

For hearts that rent and lost,
Fighting continues, hope is new.

Hand in hand is how we stand,
To lose the chains, to heal the land.

Love is our shield and truth our sword,
We'll shine a light; we'll make a noise,
For because every soul must have a choice.

